

EXPLORERS

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Virginia Tech

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering

Network Science, Wireless, and Security Laboratory

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Virginia Tech is the commonwealth's most comprehensive university and a leading research institution, with more than 34,000 students and a research portfolio of more than \$531 million, the largest of any university in Virginia.

As the country's fourth-largest ECE department, The Bradley Department of ECE at Virginia Tech offers strong education and research opportunities in diverse areas, including computers, control systems, wireless communications, machine learning, electronics, electromagnetics, and power. The ECE department is participating in the NGI Explorer program through its Wireless@VT research group as well as the **Network Science, Wireless, and Security Laboratory**, that are engaged in fundamental research at the intersection of wireless networking, Internet of Things, security, machine learning, and network science.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGE

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Wireless Networks
Energy
Security
Autonomous Systems
UAVs

CHALLENGE #13 - VT-ML-01

→ Distributed Machine Learning

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

The goal of this challenge is to design new machine learning techniques that can perform training and inference in a distributed manner, over massive Internet of Things systems. This involves designing new distributed learning mechanisms that can operate over large-scale systems in a communication efficient and secure manner. This involves addressing technical issues at the intersection of machine learning, wireless communications, game theory, optimization, and security.

OBJECTIVES

Researchers will be involved in cutting edge research that bridges the gap between various disciplines that involve learning, communications, and statistics. The goal is to address fundamental research problems related to distributed learning and to publish findings in top-tier venues.

SKILLS REQUIRED

Applicants must have a drive for pursuing fundamental research with an intent to publish in top-tier conference and journal venues. Candidates must have a background in machine learning, communications, and/or adjunct areas and a strong research track-record that includes prior publications in journal and conference venues.

